

**Massive Open Online Course
FROM SWAB TO SERVER: TESTING, SEQUENCING AND SHARING DURING A
PANDEMIC**

About the course

Sampling and testing are key to understanding where a disease is spreading. In the COVID-19 pandemic, the number of samples taken, analysed, tracked and shared have far surpassed any previous pandemic. This course follows the journey of a sample from the swab to the processed data used by experts in pandemic response. It discusses how to share data across teams and internationally, and the ethical and practical implications of using mass data on a pandemic scale.

Learning outcomes

- Outline the journey from sample collection, through PCR to sequencing and data linkage
- Compare the different sample types and how sampling strategy affects test performance
- Explain the importance of linking genomic data to clinical and epidemiological data sets to address public health and scientific questions
- Identify and explore ethical, legal and social implications of data use and sharing

Target audience

This course is for researchers, healthcare and public health professionals, diagnostic professionals, or any person involved in testing and analysis of disease samples.

Material repository website

https://wcscourses.github.io/COG-Train_Resources/swab_to_server_home.html

Content

Week 1 - The journey of a sample

Glossary

The testing pathway

Comparing different types of testing

PCR testing in the COVID-19 pandemic

Sample types for testing

Walkthrough of the sequencing process

How to avoid the pitfalls and get trustable results?

Understanding the different sources of samples for testing

Importance of taking an appropriate sample

The role of quality management

High-throughput testing during pandemic response

Scaling up: implementation and how to overcome limitations

Week 2 - How to make data richer

How different countries tackled the pandemic: an example

Introduction to biobanking

Walking through a biobank

What is metadata?

Types of metadata

Data collection tools

Public databases benefit epidemiology

Ensuring sample/data consent and ownership

Data enrichment benefits to epidemiology

Benefits and challenges of integrating clinical data

Practical challenges: setting up a laboratory during lockdown

De-centralising genomic surveillance

Week 3 - A sample without data is nothing

Lessons learnt: how to be prepared for the next pandemic

Data sharing in “peace” and “war” time

Stakeholders for data sharing and the importance to share

Opportunities for global collaboration in pathogen genomics

Challenges and limitations of data sharing

Data sharing best practices

The FAIR principles

How do FAIR principles apply in a public health emergency

No database is perfect: beware of errors in sequence databases

How to establish fruitful and fair collaboration: an example

How to promote data sharing

Importance of implementing local capacity

Resources

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